

NOTES

6. R. J. ANDERSON, R. L. SHRINER and G. O. BURN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, **48**, 2993.
7. W. J. THOMPSON, W. E. ROBBINS and G. L. BAKER, *Steroid*, 1963, **2**, 505; E. FERNHOLZY and W. L. RNIH, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, **63**, 1157.

Compounds were synthesized according to following steps.

1. 2-methyl 6,7 or 8 benz. substituted 4-hydroxy quinolines were prepared by the previous reported method⁷.
2. 2-methyl 6,7 or 8 benz. substituted 4-chloro-quinolines were prepared by method reported in literature⁸.
3. Substituted amino acid ester hydrochlorides were prepared by reported method⁹.

Amoebicidal and Fungicidal Activity in New Quinolines

S. AHMAD*, R. C. GUPTA, K. SHANKER, R. NATH,
K. P. BHARGAVA and K. KISHOR**

Department of Pharmacology, K. G's Medical College, Lucknow
*Manuscript received 20 October 1978, revised 12 April 1979,
accepted 6 October 1979*

QUINOLINE compounds have an effective role in the therapy of microbial diseases. Its significance regarding amoebiasis is well established by the introduction of well known drugs like diidoquin, chloroquin etc.¹⁻³.

The development of 8-hydroxy quinoline as a reputed clinically effective fungitoxic led to the recognition of quinoline group as antifungal agents³⁻⁴, extensive investigation has indicated that not only the 8-hydroxy quinoline but several derivatives of quinoline, which may or may not have 8-hydroxy substitution also possess good fungitoxic effects⁵⁻⁶.

These observations prompted us to synthesize compounds with various amino acids incorporated in the quinoline nucleus at position 4 and thirteen of them tested for antimicrobial activity.

Synthesis of 2-methyl 6,7 or 8 benz. substituted 4-amino substituted carboethoxy quinolines :

Substituted 4-chloro quinolines (0.01 moles) and amino acids ester hydrochloride (0.01 mole) were taken in ethoxy ethanol (15 ml) anhydrous K₂CO₃ (0.02 mole) was added to it and mixture was refluxed for 24 hrs. The reaction mixture was cooled and filtered. Ethoxy ethanol was removed under reduced pressure, the residue was mixed with water, made alkaline with NaOH solution and extracted with Et₂O, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and ether was evaporated. The solid mass obtained was characterized by mps, analysis and I.R. and listed in Table 1.

The presence of characteristic bands of NH (3200 cm⁻¹), C=O(1680 cm⁻¹), C-O stretching of ester linkage (1340 cm⁻¹; 1170 cm⁻¹) and C=N (1610 cm⁻¹) in the infra-red spectrum of 6-methoxy-2-methyl 4-(aminoethyl propionate) quinoline and characteristic bands of NH(3210 cm⁻¹) C=O (1685 cm⁻¹), C-O stretching of ester linkage (1250 cm⁻¹; 1160 cm⁻¹) and C=N (1600 cm⁻¹) in

TABLE 1—6,7,8 BENZ. SUBSTITUTED 2-METHYL, 4-(AMINO SUBSTITUTED) CARBOETHOXY QUINOLINES

Compd. No.	X	R	Yield %	M.P. °C	Formula	N%		Amoebicidal activity at 1:1000 dilution against <i>S. russelli</i>
						Calcd.	Found	
1.	6-CH ₃	CHCH(CH ₃) ₂	40	76	C ₁₈ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₂	9.33	9.54	

* Part of Ph.D. Thesis of S. Ahmad.

** Enquiries should be addressed to K. Kishor.

(Table 1 Contd.)

2.	6-CH ₃		40	74	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂	10.88	10.82
3.	6-CH ₃		50	70	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂	10.29	10.86
4.	6-OCH ₃		40	85	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂	8.85	8.74
5.	6-OH		45	80	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂	10.50	10.25
6.	6-OCH ₃		55	100	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂	9.72	9.97
7.	6-OCH ₃		45	85	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂	10.21	10.24
8.	6-OCH ₃		70	140	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂	8.76	8.96
9.	6-OCH ₃		50	75	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂	9.2	10.28
10.	6-OCH ₃		50	85	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂	9.72	9.56
11.	6-Cl		45	104	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ Cl	9.57	10.72
12.	6-Cl		50	116	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂ Cl	10.07	9.94
13.	6-Cl		55	104	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂ Cl	10.30	10.18
14.	8-OC ₂ H ₅		55	84	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂	8.48	8.56
15.	8-OCH ₃		50	80	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂	10.21	10.52
16.	7-CH ₃		50	210	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂	10.65	10.42
17.	7-OH		50	150	C ₉ H ₈ N ₂ O ₂	10.88	10.62
18.	8-CH ₃		40	130	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂	9.33	9.12
19.	8-CH ₃		45	100	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂	10.88	10.94

NOTES

(Table 1 Contd.)

20.	7-Cl	-CH ₂ -	74	50	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂ Cl	10.05	10.22	
21.	7-Cl		64	50	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂ Cl	10.3	9.48	
22.	8-OC ₂ H ₅	-CH ₂ -	116	45	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂	9.7	10.42	
23.	8-OCH ₃		70	45	C ₁₇ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂	8.81	9.44	
24.	8-OCH ₃	-CH ₂ CH ₃	55	100	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂	9.7	10.42	±
25.	8 OCH ₃		50	85	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂	10.42	10.54	

(-) negative culture ; (+) positive culture ; (±) dead and alive amoebae.

TABLE 2—ANTIFUNGAL SCREENING OF 2-METHYL 6, 7 or 8 BENZ. SUBSTITUTED 4-AMINO SUBSTITUTED CARBOETHOXY QUINOLINES

Compd. No.	<i>Asp. niger</i>	<i>A. terreus</i>	<i>Asp. nidulans</i>	<i>A. tenuis</i>	<i>P. funiculosum</i>	<i>C. lunata</i>
Control	++++	++++	++++	++++	++++	++++
4.	++	++	+++	++±	+++	+++
5.	-	-	±	+	-	+
6.	++	++	+±	+++	++	++
7.	++++	+++	++++	++±	+++	++++
8.	++	++±	++	+++	++	++++
9.	+	++	+±	+	+	+
25.	++	+++	++±	+++	++	+++
24.	-	+	±	-	+	±
16.	+++	+++	+++	++++	++	+++
18.	+	+	++	++	++	++
19.	-	-	-	+	±	-
15.	++	++	++	+++	++	+
17.	+	++	+±	++	+	±

++ to ++++ = Good growth, positive utilization and no fungicidal activity.

± to +± = Slight growth, slight fungicidal activity.

- = No growth, fungicidal activity.

Compounds are in the same serial No. as indicated in Table 1.

infra-red spectrum of 6-methoxy 2-methyl-4-(amino-isovelanine) quinoline provided the support for the structures of these quinolines.

Compound Nos 5, 19 and 24 were found good fungicidal while Compound Nos 9, 17 and 18 were slight fungicidal.

*Pharmacological screening*¹⁰ :

Determination of amoebicidal activity against Schizopyrenus russelli in vitro :

The amoebae of *S. russelli* were grown in mono-bacterial cultures of non-nutrient agar plates (2.5% w/v agar ; 5% w/v NaCl, pH 6.8-7.0) supplied with a young culture of *Escherichia coli* (2-3 days old grown on nutrient agar slages as food). A dash of fresh *E. coli* was added to freshly harvested amoebae (in 5% saline) to keep the amoebae motile and stretched. One drop of this suspension was taken in each cavities of the cavity slide and to it double the amount of drug concentration (aqueous solution) to be tested (to compensate for the dilution) was added. Slides were incubated in moist chamber at 25±1° for 24 hrs. After 24 hrs the amoebae were once again observed for judging their viability (Table 2).

Determination of Fungicidal Activity :

Six species of fungi were used in the present study *Aspergillus niger*, *Apergillus terreus*, *Aspergillus nidulans*, *Alternaria tennus*, *Penicillium funiculo-sum*, *Carbularia lunata*. Sabouard's broth (peptone 10.0 gm/litre, dextrose 20.0 gm/litre, pH 6.0 approx.) was used as the test medium, compounds were dissolved in alcohol. 1.0 ml of test solution (100 µg/ml) was added to each tube containing equal amount of media. Tubes were autoclaved at 15 lbs for 15 minutes prior to inoculation tubes were incubated at 26±2° for 7 days and the vegetative growth recorded visually in each case (Table 2).

Results and Discussion

13 of the synthesized compounds were tested for amoebicidal and fungicidal activity *in vitro* and reported in Tables 1 and 2. Compound Nos 5,7,9, 15, 16, 18 and 19 showed amoebicidal activity and compound Nos. 4,6,17 and 24 showed slight amoebi-cidal activity at 1 : 1000 dilution and in Table 2

Acknowledgement

One of us (S.A.) is thankful to I.C.M.R. for providing financial Assistance.

References

1. A. L. ELSLAGER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **78**, 3453.
2. W. SHORT, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **80**, 223.
3. H. GERSHON, W. MAYHARD and M. C. NEIL, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1972, **15**, 987.
4. H. GERSHON, W. MAYHARD and M. C. NEIL, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1970, **13**, 105.
5. G. O. WRIGHT, J. E. GRAY and C. NIEMYR, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1974, **17**, 244.
6. A. D. FILTEN and K. RIDGWAY, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1970, **13**, 1008.
7. V. K. MEHTA and S. R. PATEL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1966, **43**, 235.
8. V. K. MEHTA and D. R. PATEL and S. R. PATEL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **45**, 633.
9. A. B. SEN and M. S. YAJNIK, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **42**, 145.
10. R. C. GUPTA, R. NATH, K. SHANKER, K. P. BHARGAVA and K. KISHOR, *Indian J. Pharm.*, 1977, **39**, 111.